

Genus *Crotalaria* X. Methylethers of Supinidine and Heliotridine from *C. medicaginea* Lamk.

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Investigation of the seeds of *C. medicaginea* has revealed the presence of two alkaloids identified as 1-methoxymethyl-1, 2-dehydro-8 α -pyrrolizidine and 7 α -hydroxy-1-methoxymethyl-1, 2-dehydro-8 α -pyrrolizidine. The structures are derived on the basis of spectral and chemical evidence.

The seeds of *C. medicaginea* have been reported to contain two liquid alkaloids A ($C_9H_{15}NO$, b.p. 78–80°/25 mm) and B ($C_9H_{15}NO_2$, b.p. 180–183°/35 mm) by Sethi and Atal¹. Later on Seshadri and coworkers² recorded the isolation of a single unidentified base $C_9H_{15}NO_2$ which appears to be none other than base B of Sethi and Atal. Culvenor *et al.*³ have published the presence of methylether of heliotridine alongwith other bases from *C. trifoliatrum* Willd., a species which is taxonomically very close to *C. medicaginea*.

In the present communication we have confirmed from spectral and chemical evidence that bases A and B are 1 methoxymethyl, 1-2-dehydro-8- α -pyrrolizidine (I) and 7 α -hydroxy-1-methoxymethyl-1,2-dehydro-8 α -pyrrolizidine (II), the methylethers of supinidine and heliotridine respectively.

4.6 kg. dehusked powdered seeds were defatted with petroleum ether and subsequently extracted with methanol. Solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the resulting material was stirred with 4 × 300 ml. of 0.5 N sulphuric acid and filtered. The filtrate was washed with chloroform, basified with ammonia and extracted with chloroform (5 × 500 ml.). Removal of chloroform yielded 22.5 g. crude bases. To the aqueous solution was added 100 ml. sodium hydroxide and further extractions with chloroform gave additional 3.5 g. crude bases. The crude mixture on TLC (slurry made from silica gel G with N/10 sodium hydroxide, using solvent system : chloroform-methanol-ammonia 85 : 14 : 1) showed two

1. M. L. Sethi and C. K. Atal, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1963, **25**, 159.
2. R. N. Gandhi, T. R. Rajagopalan and T. R. Seshadri, *Curr. Sci.*, 1966, **35**, 460.
3. C. C. J. Culvenor, G. M. O'Donovan and L. W. Smith, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 757.

spots having R_f 0.28 (I) and 0.16 (II). The whole lot was distilled under reduced pressure. Base (I) 40 mg. distilled at 85–95°/10 mm. while the base II (10.1 g.) was obtained at 130–138°/10 mm.

The liquid base (I) is confirmed to be the methyl ether of supinidine on the basis of its picrate m.p. and m.m.p. 153–54° (Found : N, 14.4% Calc. for $C_9H_{15}ON.C_6H_3O_7N_3$: N, 14.6%) and its IR and NMR fully agreed with the corresponding spectra of methyl ether of supinidine isolated by Culvenor and Smith⁴ from *C. trifoliatrum* Willd.

The base (II) fraction was a pale yellow fluorescent liquid which crystallised on keeping in the refrigerator. It was recrystallised from ether to give 6.2 g. of fine colourless crystals m.p. 62–62.5° (reported³ for methyl ether of heliotridine 54°), $(\alpha)_D^{39} + 27^\circ$ (ethanol) picrate m.p. 160° (reported³ 160–160.5°). (Found, C, 45.13; H, 4.60; N, 14.46%. Calc. for $C_9H_{15}O_2N.C_6H_3O_7N_3$: C, 45.2; H, 4.6; N, 14.1%). The structure (II) is further established from the following sequence of reactions :

(a) 7-Chloro-1-methoxymethyl-1,2-dehydro-8 α -pyrrolizidine (III) : 2.0 g. of (II) on treatment⁴ with 16.5 ml. of thionylchloride yielded 1.83 g. of (III) having R_f 0.63 (t.l.c.). The picrate crystallised as yellow needles from ethanol, m.p. 152–152.5° (Found : N, 12.90% Calc. for $C_9H_{14}ONCl.C_6H_3O_7N_3$: N, 13.4%). The m.p. of picrate of 7-chloro derivative from the corresponding 7- β -hydroxy compound is reported⁴ to be 126.5–127°.

(b) 1- β -Methoxymethyl-8 α -pyrrolizidine (IV) : Compound (III) (1.70 g.) on hydrogenation in absolute alcohol over Raney nickel absorbed 2 moles of hydrogen. The product when distilled in a bulb tube (oven temp. 100–110°/10 mm) yielded 595 mg. of colourless liquid (IV) having R_f 0.15 (t.l.c.). It crystallises on cooling but is hygroscopic in nature. The picrate crystallised as yellow needles from ethanol, m.p. 166–167° (reported⁴ 169°). (Found : N, 14.2%, Calc. for $C_9H_{17}ON.C_6H_3O_7N_3$: N, 14.6%).

(c) (–)-Isoretronecanol (V) : 500 mg. of (IV) was heated gently with 1.6 ml. HBr (48%) for 4 hrs. The product was further worked up⁴ giving 200 mg. of V which yielded crystalline picrate from ethanol m.p. and m.m.p. 190–191° (Found : N, 14.42%, Calc. for $C_8H_{15}ON.C_6H_3O_7N_3$, N, 15.1%).

IR and NMR of base (II) were identical to the corresponding spectra of methyl ether of heliotridine.

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